

Deciphering the functions of individual domains of the Tomato Golden Mosaic Virus Replication-initiator protein using fluorescently labelled DNA

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Introduction

Circular Rep-encoding single-stranded DNA (CRESS-DNA) viruses belong to the phylum of *Cressdnaviricota* with an extremely broad host range including animals and plants. They share a circular single-stranded DNA genome structure and encode the Replication initiator protein (Rep) as a common denominator of this group of viruses [1-3]. The CRESS-DNA virus family of *Geminiviridae* poses a serious economic threat to important crops including cassava, cucurbits, maize, tomato and wheat [4]. Rep is the only viral protein critical for viral DNA replication *via* rolling-circle replication (RCR) and fulfils multiple functions in this DNA replication process [5, 6]. Rep proteins comprise three functional domains: (i) an N-terminal HUH- (histidine (H) – hydrophobic residue (U) – histidine (H)-) endonuclease domain which recognises the origin of replication (*ori*) of the viral DNA, nicks the DNA, and covalently attaches to the 5'-end of the nicked site [7, 8]; (ii) a central oligomerisation domain that promotes Rep oligomer formation [9]; and (iii) a C-terminal SF3 (Superfamily 3) AAA+ (ATPases Associated with diverse cellular Activities) domain with helicase activity [10, 11]. Oligomerisation of Rep is a prerequisite to exert its helicase activity [10]. In the geminivirus Tomato Golden Mosaic Virus (TGMV), the boundaries and properties of the domains of Rep (also called AL1), including the endonuclease activity of the HUH domain, have been studied earlier [9, 11, 24]. However, the DNA-binding capacity of the C-terminal ATPase domain has not been addressed in previous studies. Here we describe a protocol to study the interaction of the individual domains of TGMV-Rep with DNA using fluorescently labelled DNA probes. Applying this protocol, we confirm the endonuclease activity of the N-terminal domain of TGMV-Rep. In addition, we show that (i) DNA binding of the C-terminal domain is independent of the DNA sequence, but that (ii) a minimum length (number of nucleotides) is required for binding and that (iii) ssDNA is likely preferred over dsDNA.

Results

TGMV-Rep can be divided into two halves that show distinct functions

To examine whether (i) the individual endonuclease and ATPase domains are capable of performing their designated functions independently of each other and (ii) the oligomerisation domain is sufficient to promote oligomerisation, we designed truncated variants of the full-length TGMV-Rep based on a predicted protein model. Three-dimensional structure prediction with AlphaFold2 [25, 26] suggests the presence of three individual domains in TGMV-Rep connected by long flexible linkers, as described in earlier studies [11, 23]. Comparisons with existing experimental structures revealed that the N-terminal domain shares high overall structural similarity with the HUH-endonuclease domain (ED) of Reps from Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Virus (TYLCV [*Begomovirus coheni*], PDB: 7VG8), Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Sardinia Virus (TYLCSV [*Begomovirus solanumflavusardiniaense*], PDB: 1L2M, 1L5I), Wheat Dwarf Virus (WDV [*Mastrevirus hordei*], PDB: 6Q1M, 6WE0, 6WE1) and *Porcine circovirus 2* (PCV2, PDB: 2HW0, 6WDZ), whereas the central and the C-terminal domains structurally resemble the oligomerisation domain (OD) and the superfamily 3 (SF3) ATPase domain (AD) of PCV2 Rep (PDB: 7LAR, 7LAS) [10, 27-30].

The two constructs investigated in this study comprise either the N-terminal endonuclease domain (ED) in tandem with the central oligomerisation domain (OD) and a short C-terminal linker (termed Rep-N, residues Met1-Glu179), or a short N-terminal linker followed by the central OD and the C-terminal ATPase domain (AD) (termed Rep-C, residues Gln129-Ser352) (**Figure 1A**).

Figure 1: Design and analysis of the truncated versions of TGMV-Rep. (A) Rep-N comprises the N-terminal endonuclease (ED, pink), the central oligomerisation domain (OD, grey) and a short linker. Rep-C consists of a short linker region, the central oligomerisation domain (OD, grey) and the C-terminal ATPase domain (AD, yelloworange). **(B)** SDS-PAGE gel showing the purity of the two protein fragments of Rep (5 μ g of purified protein each).

Analysis of the purified constructs using SDS-PAGE confirmed that both TGMV-Rep variants could be obtained at a high degree of purity (**Figure 1B**), and the identities of the proteins as well as their expected molecular weights (Rep-N: 20728.33 Da, Rep-C: 25761.97 Da) were confirmed by electrospray ionisation mass-spectrometry (ESI-MS).

ED of Rep is sufficient for DNA cleavage

The HUH-endonuclease domain recognises and nicks the *ori* of the viral DNA, thereby forming a covalent adduct with the 5'-end of the nicking site [7, 8]. To assess whether the N-terminal HUH-endonuclease domain (ED) of TGMV-Rep is sufficient to promote the cleavage and covalent attachment of ssDNA to Rep, we performed a DNA cleavage assay using Rep-N and different ssDNA probes that contained a fluorescent label (Cy5) at their 3'-end (**Figure 2A**). The DNA probes comprised the cognate nonanucleotide *ori* sequence (pink, cleavage site indicated by an asterisk), which was identified for TGMV-Rep in an earlier study [29] alone (Probe 1) or in conjunction with 5'- and/or 3'-extensions resembling additional stretches of the stem-loop at the 5'- (green) or 3'- (blue) position of the 9-nt core element (Probes 2-4)[29]. To confirm sequence-specificity of Rep-N, we also designed a non-cleavable probe (Probe 5) by exchanging four nucleotides of the 9-nt core element, which prevents secondary-structure (*i.e.* loop) formation [29].

The ssDNA probes were each incubated with Rep-N and Rep-C, which was used as negative control (**Figure S1B**), and subsequently run on an SDS-PAGE gel. Immediately after electrophoresis, the Cy5 fluorescence signal was detected in the gel by fluorescence imaging at 675-725 nm using an excitation wavelength range of 625-650 nm. Thereafter, the gel was stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue R250. The fluorescent bands for Rep-N with Probes 1-4 (P1-P4) (**Figure 2B, left panel**) indicate the covalent attachment of the nucleotides located 3' of the cleavage site (*), which also contain the Cy5 fluorescence marker. Moreover, the shift in molecular weight of the probes P1 and P2 compared to P3 and P4 (magenta and blue arrowheads) coincides with the size difference of the 3'-arm that contains additional bases of the stem-loop in P3 and P4. In contrast to probes P1-P4, no fluorescent band was detected for P5, which suggests that this DNA sequence was not recognised by Rep-N. The Coomassie stain (**Figure 2B, right panel**) confirms the presence of Rep-N in all reactions as well as the presence of

of > 10 nt (**Figure 3B, left panel**), and the presence of Rep-C at the same positions was confirmed by Coomassie stain (**Figure 3B, right panel**). These results indicate that Rep-C interacts with ssDNA independent of the nucleotide sequence, and that variations in length between 13 and 19 nt can be accommodated.

Figure 3: ssDNA-binding activity of Rep-C. (A) Scheme of the DNA probes used for the Rep-C-ssDNA interaction assay including ssDNA probes of various lengths and sequences with fluorescent labels either at their 5'- or 3'-end. (B) Native PAGE for Rep-C-ssDNA interaction showing the fluorescent signal (Cy5, left panel) and Coomassie stain (right panel). For comparison, Rep-C alone and P3 alone were also loaded on the gel.

Rep-C prefers ssDNA over dsDNA

Since SF3 ATPases translocate along ssDNA during the process of dsDNA unwinding, we assessed if Rep-C showed a preference for either ssDNA or dsDNA. For this purpose, we used probes P3 and P7, which both comprise 15 nt in length but differ in their sequence and location of the fluorescence label, with P3 and P7 being labelled at the 3' and 5'-ends, respectively (**Figure 3A**). To generate dsDNA, both probes were annealed to their respective complementary ssDNA of the same length, and the success of annealing was confirmed using a 20 % 19:1 Acrylamide/Bisacrylamide TBE gel (**Figure S3**). Rep-C was then incubated with either ssDNA (P3 or P7) only, dsDNA (P3 or P7) only, or an equal ratio of ss- and dsDNA (P3 or P7), and the reactions were subsequently analysed by native PAGE.

A fluorescence (Cy5) signal (**Figure 4A, B, left panel**) was observed at a similar height as the protein bands (**Figure 4A, B, right panel**) for both DNA probes (P3 and P7). However, the fluorescence was slightly weaker when the Rep-C was incubated with dsDNA only along with a slight upward shift of the band compared to the reactions that contained only the ssDNA probes. The effect was reversed when both ss- and dsDNA probes were present at equimolar level, suggesting that the ssDNA outcompetes the dsDNA for binding of Rep-C.

Figure 4: Competition assay of Rep-C binding ssDNA vs. dsDNA. (A) Native PAGE of Rep-C interacting with Probe 3 (15 nt, 3'-Cy5) in single-stranded form (P3, ss), double-stranded form (P3, ds) or an equimolar amount of both single-stranded and double-stranded P3 species. DNA probes without Rep-C have been applied for comparison. The fluorescent signal (Cy5) is shown in the left panel, and Coomassie stain in the right panel. **(B)** Similar to A, except that Probe 7 (P7: 15 nt, 5'-Cy5) was used instead of Probe 3.

Materials and methods

Construct design and cloning

3D structural predictions were conducted with AlphaFold2 [25, 26] *via* the ColabFold server. The domain boundaries and linker regions of TGMV-Rep were visualised using Open-Source PyMOL and the cutting sites between (i) the N-terminal ED and the central OD, resulting in the Rep-C construct, and (ii) between the central OD and the C-terminal AD, resulting in the Rep-N construct, were assigned based on those predictions. Both constructs comprised slightly shorter linker regions compared to the TGMV-Rep truncations used in previous studies [11, 23]. Inserts of the truncated variants of TGMV-Rep were amplified from a vector which contained full-length TGMV-Rep (GenBank ID: NC_001507.1) using the respective primers (Eurofins) for Rep-N (*Rep-N_fw*, *Rep-N_rv*) and Rep-C (*Rep-C_fw*, *Rep-C_rv*) (**Table 1**) containing overhangs complementary to the target vector flanks. A customised pGEX vector with an N-terminal GST-tag and a human rhinovirus (HRV) 3C protease cleavage site was amplified using *pGEX_fw* and *pGEX_rv* and the inserts of Rep-N or Rep-C were introduced into the vector through sequence- and ligation-independent cloning (SLIC) [32]. Cloning success was verified by Sanger sequencing.

Table 1: Primers used to generate truncated versions of TGMV-Rep.

Primer name	Sequence (5' → 3')
<i>Rep-N_fw</i>	GTTCTGTTCCAGGGGCCCATGCCATCGCATCCAAAAC
<i>Rep-N_rv</i>	GACATCTACAAGGAGCGGTCATTCAGGAGTCTTATCAAATATCCTATC
<i>Rep-C_fw</i>	GTTCTGTTCCAGGGGCCCAAACATCTAACGACGCTGCAG
<i>Rep-C_rv</i>	GACATCTACAAGGAGCGGTCAGCTGCTCTGTGTTGAGCT
<i>pGEX_fw</i>	CCGCTCCTTGATAGTGC
<i>pGEX_rv</i>	GGGCCCTGGAACAG

Protein expression and purification

E. coli BL21 GOLD (DE3) cells were transformed with the pGEX vector containing DNA fragments that coded for either the Rep-N or Rep-C variant. LB medium was inoculated with transformed cells from an overnight culture at a starting OD₆₀₀ of \approx 0.1. Cells were grown at 37 °C under constant shaking and as soon as an OD₆₀₀ of 0.7 was reached, the temperature was lowered to 18 °C and protein expression was induced by adding IPTG at a final concentration of 0.5 mM. 20 h after induction, the cells were harvested at 5000 \times *g* for 15 min and the pellets were stored at -20 °C until further use.

For cell lysis, cell pellet from 1 l of liquid cell culture were resuspended in 15 ml lysis buffer (50 mM Tris/HCl, pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 10 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.5 mM CaCl₂, 2 mM DTT, 1 % (v/v) Tween-20, 1 mM PMSF). Lysozyme and DNase I (both Sigma-Aldrich) were added in powder form and the resuspended cells were stirred at 4 °C for 1 h. Thereafter, the cells were passed through a pre-cooled French pressure cell press on ice and cell debris were removed by centrifugation for 1 h at 50000 \times *g* and 4 °C.

The following chromatography steps were performed at 4 °C and protein samples were constantly kept on ice. The clarified lysate was applied to an XK 26 column packed with Glutathione Sepharose 4 Fast Flow (Cytiva) attached to an ÄKTA FPLC system (Cytiva), which was pre-equilibrated with low-salt (LS) buffer (50 mM Tris/HCl, pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 5 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM DTT). Unbound protein was washed out with 1.5 column volumes (CV) LS buffer, followed by 1.5 CV high-salt (HS) buffer

(50 mM Tris/HCl, pH 7.5, 800 mM NaCl, 5 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM DTT) and the column was equilibrated with 1.5 CV LS buffer. Subsequently, 2 mg of HRV 3C protease were circulated over the column overnight until the UV absorbance at 280 nm was stable. The cleaved Rep was then eluted from the column using ≈ 1.5 CV LS buffer or until the UV₂₈₀ signal reached a minimum and submitted to further chromatography steps, while the remaining GST-tagged Rep and free GST remained bound to the resin and were discarded.

Unlike Rep-C that was subjected to size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) after the affinity step, the Rep-N eluate from the affinity column was diluted 10-fold with IEX buffer (20 mM Hepes/NaOH, pH 7.0, 20 mM NaCl, 2.5 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM DTT), filtered through a Triton-free 0.22 μm pore size filter (Merck Millipore) and loaded onto a HiTrap SP HP cation-exchange chromatography column, pre-equilibrated with the same buffer. The column was washed with 6 CV of IEX buffer and thereafter with 8 CV of IEX buffer containing 300 mM NaCl. Rep-N was eluted using a salt gradient ranging from 300 to 500 mM NaCl over 22 CV.

For SEC, the Rep variants were concentrated to a volume of 2.5-5.0 ml using a spin concentrator (Merck Millipore). A HiLoad 16/60 Superdex 200 pg column was equilibrated with SEC buffer (20 mM Hepes/NaOH, pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 2.5 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM DTT) and the respective protein was applied to the column and separated from remaining impurities through isocratic elution. Fractions containing Rep-N or Rep-C were pooled and concentrated to final concentrations of 13.7 or 14.8 mg/ml, respectively, using a spin concentrator (Merck Millipore). Aliquots were flash-frozen with liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until further use.

Rep-N Endonuclease assay

Rep-N or Rep-C (as negative control) was diluted in reaction buffer (20 mM Hepes/NaOH, pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 2.5 % (v/v) glycerol, 5 mM MnCl₂, 2 mM DTT) to a final concentration of 16.5 μM Rep-N, or 13.4 μM Rep-C. In the case of Rep-N 660 nM of the Cy5-labelled ssDNA (Eurofins) were added; for Rep-C 536 nM of Cy5-labelled ssDNA (Eurofins) were added and the reaction was incubated for 30 min at room temperature. For the Rep-only controls, an equal volume of water was added instead of Cy5-labelled ssDNA. The samples were then loaded onto a 12.5 % SDS gel for electrophoresis. Gels were connected to a cooling system and run at 100 V for 10 min. and thereafter at 180 V for 65 min. Immediately after electrophoresis, the Cy5 fluorescence signal was detected in the gel by fluorescence imaging using an emission filter (675-725 nm) at an excitation wavelength range of 625-650 nm. Thereafter, the gel was stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue R250 to detect all protein. A ChemiDoc MP Imaging System (Bio-Rad) was used for imaging the gels (both fluorescence and protein).

Rep-C ssDNA and ss-/dsDNA-binding assays

Rep-C was diluted in reaction buffer (20 mM Hepes/NaOH, pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 2.5 % (v/v) glycerol, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM DTT) to a final concentration of 20.1 μM, and 40.2 μM of Cy5-labelled ssDNA (Eurofins) were added to test binding of ssDNA probes of different lengths. For the competition assay of ssDNA vs. dsDNA binding to Rep-C, Rep-C was diluted to a final concentration of 10.0 μM in reaction buffer, and 40.0 μM of Cy5-labelled dsDNA (Eurofins) or 40.0 μM Cy5-labelled ssDNA (Eurofins), or a mixture containing 20.0 μM of Cy5-labelled dsDNA and 20.0 μM of Cy5-labelled ssDNA were added and the reaction was incubated for 60 min on ice. The samples were then loaded onto a NativePAGE 4-16 % native Bis-Tris gel (Invitrogen) for electrophoresis and gels were run at 120 V for 150 min at 4 °C in NativePAGE Bis-Tris Running Buffer (Invitrogen). Immediately after electrophoresis, the Cy5

fluorescence signal was detected in the gel by fluorescence imaging at 675-725 nm using an excitation wavelength range of 625-650 nm. Thereafter, the gel was stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue R250. A ChemiDoc MP Imaging System (Bio-Rad) was used for gel imaging (fluorescence and protein).

Annealing of ssDNA probes

Probes 3 and 7 were mixed at equal concentrations with their respective complementary ssDNA strand (50 μ M final concentration per ssDNA fragment) and the mixtures were heated for 5 min at 95 °C. Thereafter, the reactions were cooled down at intervals of 1 °C/min over 45 min, then transferred to room temperature and left to equilibrate to ambient temperature. Annealing success was validated using a 20 % 19:1 Acrylamide/Bisacrylamide TBE gel which was run at 100 V for 120 min at room temperature. To monitor the shift in electrophoretic mobility between the ssDNA and dsDNA, the Cy5 fluorescence signal was detected immediately after electrophoresis using a ChemiDoc MP Imaging System (Bio-Rad). To confirm DNA double-strand formation, the gel was incubated in an ethidium bromide (EtBr) solution and imaged on a InGenius3 (Syngene) imaging system upon exposure to UV lighting.

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Conflict of interest statement

H.B. is currently an employee of Rijk Zwaan and was an employee of Keygene when this study was conducted. This work was supported in part by a grant Topsector T&U (LWV19157) with support from the companies Rijk Zwaan Breeding B.V., LVS, Takii, Enza Zaden and Keygene. All companies had no role in the design of the study, data collection, and writing of the manuscript. The authors declare no other competing interests.

Supporting Information

Figure S1: SDS-PAGE of DNA probes 1-5 in the presence and absence of Rep-N or Rep-C. (A) Fluorescent signal (Cy5, left panel) and Coomassie stain (right panel) for probes 1-5 (P1-5) with and without Rep-N. The Cy5 signal indicates nicking of the probe and the covalent addition of the Cy5-labelled fragment 3' of the cleavage site to Rep-N. The pink and blue arrowheads indicate the addition of the short fragment (2 nt, Probes 1 and 2), and the long fragment including a part of the 3'-stem-loop (8 nt, Probes 3 and 4), respectively, to Rep-N. **(B)** Fluorescent signal (Cy5, left panel) and Coomassie stain (right panel) for probes 1-5 (P1-5) with and without Rep-C.

Figure S2: Native PAGE of DNA probes in the absence of Rep-C. The left panel shows the fluorescent signal (Cy5), and the right panel the Coomassie stain for probes 1-7 (P1-7) without Rep-C. For comparison, Rep-C alone and Rep-C bound to P3 have been applied to the gel.

Figure S3: SDS-PAGE of ssDNA and annealed (dsDNA) products of probes 3 and 7 (P3, P7). The left panel shows the fluorescent signal (Cy5), and the right panel the Ethidium bromide stain for single-stranded (ss) vs. annealed (ds) probes 3 and 7 (P3, P7).

Primers, plasmids and probes

Primers		
ID	Name	Sequence (5' → 3')
10306	<i>Rep-N_fw</i>	GTTCTGTTCCAGGGGCCCATGCCATCGCATCCAAAAC
11843	<i>Rep-N_rv</i>	GACATCTACAAGGAGCGGTCATTGAGGAGTCTTATCAAATATCCTATC
11841	<i>Rep-C_fw</i>	GTTCTGTTCCAGGGGCCCAAACATCTAACGACGCTGCAG
10307	<i>Rep-C_rv</i>	GACATCTACAAGGAGCGGTCAGCTGCTCTGTGTTGAGCT
10229	<i>pGEX_fw</i>	CCGCTCCTGTAGATGTC
10230	<i>pGEX_rv</i>	GGGCCCTGGAACAG

Plasmids			
ID	Name	Backbone	Insert
2436	GST-TGMV-Rep-II_pGEX	pGEX-SLIC-GST-3C	<i>TGMV-Rep-C</i>
2437	GST-TGMV-Rep-IV_pGEX	pGEX-SLIC-GST-3C	<i>TGMV-Rep-N</i>

Probes			
ID	Name	Sequence (5' → 3')	Label position
probe_16	<i>Probe 1</i>	TAATATTAC	3'
probe_17	<i>Probe 2</i>	CGTTTAATATTAC	3'
probe_18	<i>Probe 3</i>	TAATATTACCGGATG	3'
probe_19	<i>Probe 4</i>	CGTTTAATATTACCGGATG	3'
probe_22	<i>Probe 5</i>	TGAGATGAT	3'
probe_20	<i>Probe 6</i>	CCCATCGTAT	5'
probe_21	<i>Probe 7</i>	CCCATCGTATAGCAA	5'
12250	SIPCNA_ds15_blunt	TTGCTATACGATGGG	N/A *
12370	TGMV-Rep-Ori_3_rv	CATCCGGTAATATTA	N/A **

* complementary to *Probe 7*, ** complementary to *Probe 3*

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